

Loxodonta africana African savanna elephant

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Phylum: Chordata

Estimated genome size: 4 340 million DNA base pairs (4.34 Gigabases)

Organism size: 3 – 4 meters

Distribution:

Angola, Botswana, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, The Democratic Republic of the Congo, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, Somalia, South Africa, South Sudan, United Republic of Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe.

Importance:

African savanna elephants are the largest land animals and crucial ecosystem engineers. Listed as endangered by the IUCN Red list, they are vital for South African tourism. This project aims to sequence the genome of a wild bull elephant from a native KZN population, providing valuable genetic data beyond existing zoo-based or outdated sequences.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 110.47 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 8.38 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 3.16 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 98.8%

[Single: 82.7%, Duplicated: 15.3%]

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